

LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN THE UZBEKISTAN
EDUCATION SYSTEM: INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS AND
REQUIREMENTS

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Abstract: The integration of our country into the world community, the development of science and technology requires the young generation to be fluent in several foreign languages. In the context of teaching a foreign language, it creates a basis for the development of a common structure of educational and working programs, study guides, exams throughout Europe.

Keywords: world, foreign language, continuous education, mastering, community, integration.

The integration of our country into the world community, the development of science and technology requires the young generation to have a perfect knowledge of several foreign languages, which is the state education of the continuous education system based on international documents on teaching foreign languages to the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. provided by the introduction of standards.

In Europe, there are several international programs for monitoring student achievement; PISA, ISCED, CEFR, etc.

Table 1

**International monitoring of students' learning
Programs**

№	International programs	Classification
1.	PISA	<p>It is an international program conducted by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD - Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development) to evaluate the achievements of students. This program allows identifying and comparing changes in education systems in different countries, as well as evaluating the effectiveness of strategic decisions in the field of education.</p> <p>According to the PISA program, monitoring of the quality of school education is carried out in three main areas: reading skills, mathematics skills and natural science skills..</p>
2.	ISCED	<p>International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) is an international standard classification of education, a document designed to classify and present international comparative statistics. The current version of the document was approved at the General Conference of UNESCO in 2011, and the first version was adopted in 1997. This document covers the stages of education from pre-school (level 0) to doctorate (level 8).</p>
3.	CEFR	<p>This document provides a basis for the development of a common European structure of curricula and work programs, study guides and exams in the context of foreign language learning. It provides a comprehensive description of the knowledge and skills that foreign language learners need to develop in order to effectively work and communicate in this language. This definition also</p>

		includes the cultural context of the language being studied.
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On May 8, 2013, changes were made to the state education standard for foreign languages of the continuing education system based on the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 124. These changes are part of the "European competences of knowledge of a foreign language; since it is based on the document "On learning, teaching and evaluation", we found it necessary to provide information about the goals, tasks and established levels of foreign language knowledge of this document. Council of Europe's "European foreign language competences; document on learning, teaching and assessment" is one of the internationally recognized standards

is one. This document creates a basis for the development of a common European structure of curricula and work programs, study guides, and exams in the context of foreign language teaching. It provides a comprehensive description of the extent to which foreign language learners need to develop knowledge and skills in order to effectively communicate and work in this language. This definition also includes the cultural context of the language being studied. Also, the program defines the level of skills that allow students to improve and monitor their knowledge. At the same time, this document creates conditions for communication among foreign language specialists.

In order to fulfill the tasks set, "European competences for knowledge of foreign languages" require to be comprehensive, transparent and consistent. Comprehensiveness of the document "CEFR ensures the broad application of foreign language knowledge, competences and skills and sets clear and understandable goals and objectives for all users." It is necessary to divide the CEFR into different levels that form and improve language skills, because these levels ensure the development of language skills. Transparency ensures that

information is clear and easy to understand for users. Consistency requires that the education system and its components be free of internal contradictions, that is, harmonious. In the process of learning a foreign language, it is necessary to develop general and communicative competences in its practical application. These competencies are used in practice to effectively use the language in different contexts. Monitoring helps to change or strengthen these competencies.

The state educational standard defines the following for all levels of foreign languages: the goals and objectives of the subject; teaching content; mandatory requirements for the preparation of graduates of all types of educational institutions.

The purpose of teaching a foreign language in all types of education of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to acquire communicative competence in a foreign language (linguistic, sociolinguistic, discursive, strategic) is the formation. In the table below, you can see the communicative competencies defined in the goals and tasks of learning the subject of the state educational standard. The main goal of teaching a foreign language is the formation of these competencies. Speech activity in English is divided into two types: productive and receptive. Productive activities include speaking and writing skills, and receptive activities include listening and reading skills. Types of speech activities and their classification are presented in the document "All-European Competences of Foreign Language Knowledge". This document divides general listening and reading skills into several tasks, which are defined as goals in the educational process.

The advantage of the document is that it shows the criteria for evaluating speech tasks at all levels of foreign language proficiency. In the process of evaluating a foreign language, subjective assessment is used in the assessment of productive skills and objective assessment is used in the assessment of receptive skills.

Objective assessment is in the form of questions with clear answers, which facilitates the assessment process and allows to assess many students in a short period of time. However, this type of assessment does not include the use of language in context and authentic settings, which can be a disadvantage.

Subjective assessment, on the other hand, covers speaking and writing skills and includes more ways of expressing correct answers. The disadvantage of this type of assessment can be factors that negatively affect the test results, for example, the lack of competence of the assessor, the shortcomings of assessment criteria, carelessness and inexperience.

Incorrect assessment may affect test results. This includes factors such as lack of competence of the evaluator, shortcomings of evaluation criteria, negligence and inexperience. In order to avoid these shortcomings, it is necessary to correctly and effectively create evaluation criteria.

The criteria used in the evaluation of speaking and writing skills are divided into four types: holistic, analytic, primary trait rubric, and multi-trait.

The state educational standard is based on communicative activity, person-oriented, integrative and competence approaches in learning a foreign language. Therefore, these criteria ensure the objectivity of teachers in assessing students' foreign language skills, facilitate compliance with the principles of assessment, and help objectively assess students' communicative competence.

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